

Effect of Independent Outside Directors and Board Size on Earnings Management in Saudi Family Businesses

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Abstract

Background: The Board of Directors (BOD) has greater authority in a firm and is responsible for protecting investors from manipulation and monitoring companies. Few studies have analysed this relationship in family businesses.

Objective: This study investigates the relationship between the presence of independent outside directors, board size, and earnings management in Saudi family businesses before and after COVID-19.

Methodology: The sample comprises 42 firm-year observations from 21 family firms listed on the Saudi Stock Exchange from 2019 to 2020. This study used fixed effects, random effects, and OLS regression.

Results: The findings show a relationship between independent outside directors and board size on Earnings Management (EM) in Saudi family businesses from 2019 to 2020. However, following a robustness check and after splitting the sample, the results show a negative and significant effect of board size on earnings management pre-COVID-19, as a substantial board size has a crucial role in mitigating the level of EM practices in Saudi family businesses in 2019. Still, there is no significant relationship between board size and independent outside directors on EM in Saudi family businesses post-COVID-19 due to new procedures that have faced the BOD.

Conclusion: The Board of Directors is vital in influencing the quality of financial reports. So, the study has focused on internal Corporate Governance (CG) mechanisms, such as the presence of independent outside directors and board size in family businesses.

Unique contribution: This study contributes to the literature by providing an insightful analysis of the impact of the presence of independent outside directors and board size on manipulating earnings in Saudi family businesses.

Key Recommendation: By examining the role of independent outside directors and board size on earnings management, this paper contributes to the growing body of literature that connects board structure with financial reporting quality in emerging markets. The focus on family-owned firms adds value, given their unique governance dynamics and prevalence in the Saudi economy.

Keywords: Earnings management, Board size, Independent outside directors, Family businesses, COVID-19.

Introduction

Accounting scandals at giant corporations such as Enron and WorldCom gave a general perception that managers used earnings management opportunistically (Jiraporn et al., 2008; Alshaketheep et al., 2024). These scandals have shaken the confidence of investors in companies. However, Saudi Arabia witnessed a similar case in the Anaam International Holding Group and Bishah Agriculture Development Company, which harmed the reputation of companies and the confidence of investors as a result of the spread of the earnings management phenomenon (Al-Moghaiwli, 2010; Abousweilem, 2024). Additionally, manipulating earnings causes companies to collapse and damages their reputation, which is difficult to restore. The purpose of earnings management is to alter the timing of recognition of assets acquisitions or revenue and some of the information in financial reports by using managers' estimations or judgment to produce a positive impression about the company's performance or to achieve predetermined goals (Mulford & Comiskey, 2005; Mansour et al., 2024).

The board of directors has the authority to monitor management, govern the organization, and act as a link between shareholders and management (Peasnell et al., 2000). The composition of the board of directors is critical; it must be ensured that the board size is not too small and includes a higher proportion of independent outside directors, leading to increased board independence and enhancing the company's reputation. The COVID-19 crisis began in China in December 2019 and has rapidly spread worldwide, affecting all countries' economies (World Bank, 2020). Recently, firms and BOD have faced unprecedented challenges due to COVID-19, which adversely affected the profitability of most firms (Khatib et al., 2021; Lassoued & Khanchel, 2021).

This study investigates whether Saudi family businesses manage their earnings during COVID-19 to reduce volatility and improve investor perception of the company's performance. It will also investigate whether independent outside directors and board size may help mitigate this phenomenon. The main objective of this study is to examine the impact of board characteristics on the EM phenomenon in Saudi family businesses within the context of Saudi Arabia pre- and post-COVID-19.

This study aims to understand whether Saudi family businesses manage their earnings during COVID-19 to reduce volatility and improve investor perception of the company's performance. It also investigates whether independent outside directors and board size may help mitigate this phenomenon. Hence, the main objective of this study is to examine the impact of board characteristics on the EM phenomenon in Saudi family businesses within the context of Saudi Arabia pre- and post-COVID-19.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: The next section reviews the related prior studies and develops the study's hypotheses. Section 3 illustrates the study methodology. Section 4 shows the study findings. Section 5 discusses these findings. Finally, section 6 concludes the paper.

Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

Independent outside directors and earnings management

The Board of directors consists of executives (inside directors) and non-executives (outside directors) who are frequently chosen by inside directors (Abdel-Khalik, 2002). Inside directors offer valuable information about the firm's operations, while outside directors can evaluate managers' decisions based on their expertise and objectivity (Byrd & Hickman, 1992). With a higher percentage of independent outside board members, better service can be provided to shareholders.

According to Article 16 of the Saudi Corporate Governance Regulation, the number of independent members of the directors is not less than two or one-third of the board of directors' members, whichever is greater (Capital Market Authority, 2022). In this section, the research highlights the studies related to outside independent directors and the EM phenomenon in developed and developing countries.

According to the agency, resource dependence, and upper echelons theories, the presence of independent outside directors plays a significant role in monitoring the unethical behavior of the management, resolving conflicts of interest between owner and management, and improving earnings quality. Besides, the financial experience of outside directors will bring more knowledge and networks to the board. In this paper, the relationship between the presence of independent outside directors and the EM phenomenon will be discussed in family businesses. So, the hypothesis will be as follows:

H1: *Independent outside directors mitigate EM practices in Saudi family businesses pre-COVID-19.*

H2: *Independent outside directors mitigate EM practices in Saudi family businesses post-COVID-19.*

Board size and earnings management

Board size can vary depending on the company's size and business nature. Board size is one of the internal CG mechanisms. This paper will discuss the studies related to board size and EM in developed and developing countries. The appropriate board size varies between companies and governments. There is no agreement in the previous studies regarding the relationship between board size and EM practices, whether in developed or developing countries. Therefore, the hypothesis will be as follows:

H3: *Large board size mitigates EM practice in Saudi family businesses pre-COVID-19.*

H4: *Large board size mitigates EM practice in Saudi family businesses post-COVID-19.*

Research Methodology

Research design

A quantitative correlation research design was adopted to analyse the effect of board characteristics on the EM phenomenon in Saudi Arabia (Hair et al., 2010). This method is appropriate for obtaining accurate results by measuring the effectiveness of CG mechanisms in mitigating the manipulation of earnings during unexpected periods. Additionally, to test the hypothesis and provide a deep understanding of the research problem. This study covers two years, from 2019 to 2020, pre- and post-COVID-19. The explanation for choosing this duration is to evaluate the relationship between independent and dependent variables before the outbreak of COVID-19 and the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on these variables. The study population includes all non-financial family-listed firms on the Saudi Stock Exchange (TASI). It excludes financial firms such as Banks, insurance companies, diversified financials, and REITs because they are subject to different procedures and regulations. Moreover, the effectiveness of the modified Johns model in detecting discretionary accruals in these firms has not been mentioned in the literature (Peasnell et al., 2000). Kothari et al. (2005) developed the previous models, such as Jones 1991 and the modified Jones model 1995. They improved their effectiveness by considering accruals and ROA to measure the company's performance. As the study focuses on EM during and after the COVID-19 crisis, which affects the company's performance, it is best to measure EM using the Kothari et al. (2005) model, as this model considers ROA.

Methods and data sources

The following criteria were used to select the study's sample:

- The company's data will be available for two years from 2019-2020, which is the period of this study.
- Family firms listed on the Saudi stock exchange (Tadawul) from 2019 to 2020 based on several criteria, such as:
 - The percentage of voting determines family ownership.
 - Family members run it.
 - Intergenerational ownership transfers.
 - Families own 50% or more of a company's equity.

- Family businesses have been selected for this study because 63% of businesses in Saudi Arabia are family-owned, and Saudi family businesses contribute 32% of the country's GDP and 52 % of its workforce (CMA, 2021).

Financial data was extracted from the Bloomberg database and collected manually from the Saudi Stock Exchange (Tadawul) because not all economic data is available in the Bloomberg database. Corporate governance data, such as independent outside directors and board size, was also collected manually from the Saudi Stock Exchange (Tadawul). The Bloomberg database is characterized by reliability and accuracy and covers all market sectors, making it easier for the researcher to extract and analyse data.

This paper focuses on family-listed firms and excludes all financial firms due to the different nature of these industries in terms of their establishment and inclusion (CMA, 2021) and non-family firms from 2019-2020. According to the abovementioned criteria, family businesses are distinguished from non-family businesses. Thus, the pooled final sample consists of 42 family-listed firms from 2019 to 2020.

Measurement of variables

Earnings management involves the estimation of discretionary accruals using models like the Jones (1991) and modified Jones model (Dechow et al., 1995). The modified Jones model addresses the original's shortcomings by focusing on credit sales, which can be manipulated to influence earnings (Chen, 2010). Although widely used, it faces criticism.

Kothari et al. (2005) improved upon earlier models by incorporating accruals and return on assets (ROA), making it suitable for studying earnings management (EM) during and after the COVID-19 crisis. As economies struggled, managers may have been incentivised to manage earnings upward to maintain investor confidence (Lassoued & Khanchel, 2021).

Total accruals include discretionary and non-discretionary accruals, focusing on discretionary accruals as indicators of management intervention. Additionally, effective corporate governance requires controlling variables such as firm size (FSIZ), measured by the natural log of total assets; firm profitability (ROA), defined as EBIT divided by total assets; and financial leverage (LEV), calculated as total debts divided by total assets (Khatib et al., 2021).

Research model

The aim is to examine the effect of board characteristics on the EM phenomenon in Saudi family businesses from 2019 to 2020. The following panel regression model is used:

$$ADACC_{it} = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 BIND_t + \alpha_3 BSIZ_{i,t} + \alpha_4 FSIZ_{i,t} + \alpha_5 ROA_{i,t} + \alpha_6 LEV + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Data Analysis and Findings

This section starts by analysing the statistics of variables used in this study to test the relationship between board characteristics and EM. Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of earnings management, independent outside directors, board size, firm size, firm performance, and leverage for the sample of this study. The sample has 42 firm-year observations throughout 2019-2020.

Panel A of Table 1 shows descriptive statistics of discretionary accruals (ADACC), measured by the Kothari model (2005). The mean value of (ADACC) for the sample is 0.1 and it ranges from a

minimum of 0 to a maximum of 0.55. Panel B of Table 1 shows descriptive statistics of the independent variables. The average number of independent outside directors (BIND) for the sample is 0.4, ranging from a minimum of 0.33 to a maximum of 0.62. According to the CG code in Saudi Arabia, at least one-third of the board should be independent (CMA, 2021), implying that Saudi family businesses are following the requirements of the CG code. The average board size (BSIZ) in Saudi family businesses is about seven members; it ranges from a minimum of 4 to a maximum of 9, and Saudi Arabia’s CG code suggests that the board should have at least three and no more than eleven members so, the study sample followed the requirements of the system. Panel C reports the descriptive statistics of control variables. Regarding control variables, the average firm size (FSIZ) is 21, ranging from a minimum of 18 to a maximum of 23. The mean value of firm leverage (LEV) is 0.48, ranging from a minimum of 0 to a maximum of 0.89, and on average, the firm performance (ROA) has a mean of 0.05, with a minimum value of -0.25 and a maximum value of 0.68.

The absolute value of discretionary accruals (ADACC), independent outside directors (BIND), firm profitability (ROA), and firm leverage (LEV) have a low standard deviation, meaning the data fluctuates little.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics for Saudi family businesses from 2019-2020

Variables	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Dev
Panel A: Earnings management (dependent) variable					
ADtACC	42	0.00	0.55	0.1195	0.13303
Panel B: Corporate governance (independent) variables					
BIND	42	0.3	0.6	0.430	0.0943
BSIZ	42	4.0	9.0	7.833	1.3778
Panel C: Control variables					
FSIZ	42	18.122	23.702	21.28894	1.300798
ROA	42	-0.249	0.679	0.05770	0.128837
LEV	42	0.000	0.888	0.48281	0.243258

Correlation Matrix

Table 2 shows the sample correlation matrix for the dependent, independent, and control variables used to test the relationship between board characteristics and EM in Saudi family businesses. In line with previous studies, this study uses the Pearson correlation test (Chen & Zhang, 2014). The results show that the correlation coefficient between discretionary accruals (ADACC) and firm performance (ROA) is positive and medium, implying that the greater the company's profit, the greater the likelihood of manipulating earnings. On the other hand, discretionary accruals (ADACC) are negatively correlated with the board size (BSIZ) and firm leverage (LEV), with correlation values of -0.23 and -0.06, respectively. The correlation between discretionary accruals (ADACC) and other variables is weak. Furthermore, there is a negative and significant correlation between board size (BSIZ) and independent outside directors (BIND), indicating that the larger the board size, the fewer the number of independent outside directors at the level of - 0.48. Board size (BSIZ) is significantly correlated with firm size (FSIZ), as shown in Table 2, and large family firms typically have large boards. There is a significant and negative correlation between firm

leverage (LEV) and firm profitability (ROA), with a correlation value of -0.35 in family firms, which is consistent with the study of Saidat et al. (2018).

Table 2: Pearson's Correlations of all variables for the Saudi family businesses from 2019-2020

Variables	ADACC	BIND	BSIZ	FSIZ	LEV	ROA
ADACC	1	0.034889	-0.23863	0.010956	-0.06046	0.325682
BIND	0.034889	1	-0.48006	-0.00351	0.17247	0.120036
BSIZ	-0.23863	-0.48006	1	0.388278	0.167318	-0.31633
FSIZ	0.010956	-0.00351	0.388278	1	0.517629	-0.27956
LEV	-0.06046	0.17247	0.167318	0.517629	1	-0.34843
ROA	0.325682	0.120036	-0.31633	-0.27956	-0.34843	1

Multivariate Analysis

Table 3 shows the results of regression analysis using panel data to test the relationship between the dependent variable (ADACC), independent variables (BIND and BSIZ), and control variables (FSIZ, ROA, LEV) in Saudi family businesses from 2019-2020. The results show that firm size (FSIZ) and firm performance (ROA) have a positive and significant impact on discretionary accruals (ADACC) at a one percent level; there is no significant effect of firm leverage (LEV) on discretionary accruals (ADACC) in Saudi family businesses. On the other hand, board size (BSIZ) and independent outside directors (BIND) have a negative and significant impact on discretionary accruals (ADACC) in Saudi family businesses at a one per cent level. This suggests that large board sizes and a high percentage of independent outside directors lead to manipulating earnings in Saudi family businesses. However, R^2 is 0.20, implying that approximately 20% of the dependent variable (ADACC) variance is caused by independent variables (BIND, BSIZ).

Table 3: Regression analysis results for the sample from 2019-2020 using the FE model

Variable	coefficient	t-Statistic	prob.
<i>Independent variables</i>			
BIND	-0.186652	-4.118625	0.0002
BSIZ	-0.026137	-3.147142	0.0034
<i>Control Variables</i>			
FSIZ	0.021524	4.629334	0.0000
LEV	-0.002430	-0.045914	0.9636
ROA	0.355817	47.54082	0.0000
Constant	-0.073012	-0.428157	0.6712
R^2		0.20	
F-statistics		1.49	
Prob (F-statistics)		0.20	

Regression analysis after adding dummy variables

To provide accurate results on the relationship between board characteristics and earnings management in Saudi family businesses from 2019-2020, it is necessary to add COVID-19 and industry as dummy variables. To test the hypothesis, the following panel regression model was formulated:

$$ADACC_{it} = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 BIND_t + \alpha_3 BSIZ_{i,t} + \alpha_4 FSIZ_{i,t} + \alpha_5 ROA_{i,t} + \alpha_6 LEV + \alpha_7 COVID19 + \alpha_8 INDU + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

In the above model, ADACC is taken as a dependent variable, which denotes the absolute value of discretionary accruals measured by the Kothari et al. (2005) model. BIND represents the number of independent outside directors in Saudi family businesses. BSIZ denotes board size in Saudi family businesses; hence, (BIND and BSIZ) are taken as independent variables. FSIZ represents the firm size, and ROA is firm profitability; LEV denotes firm leverage; thus, (FSIZ, ROA, and LEV) are taken as control variables. In this model, COVID-19 is a dummy variable, giving a value of 1 post-COVID-19 in 2020 and 0 pre-COVID-19 in 2019. INDUS is also a dummy variable indicating the industry to which the firm relates, and it is given a value of 1 if the firm is industrial and zero if non-industrial. So, after conducting the Hausman test, the best model is random effects for the study sample because the p-value > 0.05.

Table 4 shows the results of regression analysis using panel data to test the relationship between the dependent variable (ADACC), independent variables (BIND and BSIZ), control variables (FSIZ, ROA, LEV), and dummy variables (COVID-19 and INDUS) in Saudi family businesses from 2019-2020.

The results show that board size (BSIZ) significantly and negatively impacts discretionary accruals (ADACC) at a 1% level. However, there is no significant effect of independent outside directors (BIND) on discretionary accruals (ADACC) in Saudi family businesses, owing to a p-value > 0.05. Firm size (FSIZ) positively and significantly impacts discretionary accruals (ADACC) at a one percent level; the larger the firm's size, the more likely it is to be manipulated. On the other hand, the results show a significant and negative impact of firm performance (ROA) on discretionary accruals (ADACC), implying that the higher the firm's profitability, the less likely it is to manipulate earnings in Saudi family businesses. The firm leverage (LEV) has no significant effect on discretionary accruals (ADACC) from 2019 to 2020.

COVID-19, as a dummy variable, has a positive and significant impact on discretionary accruals (ADACC); the outbreak of COVID-19 led to an increase in the practice of earnings management in Saudi family businesses, as expected. However, industry (INDU) negatively and significantly impacts discretionary accruals (ADACC), meaning that industrial firms will be less likely to exercise earnings management in 2019 and 2020.

Table 4: Regression results for the Saudi family businesses from 2019-2020 using the RE model after adding dummy variables.

Variable	coefficient	t-Statistic	prob.
<i>Independent variables</i>			
BIND	-0.099318	-0.946036	0.3508
BSIZ	-0.026137	-3.147142	0.0000

<i>Control Variables</i>			
FSIZ	0.022394	4.989821	0.0000
LEV	-0.014067	-0.168204	0.8674
ROA	-0.126268	-4.807737	0.0000
<i>Dummy variables</i>			
COVID-19	0.031026	10.70848	0.0000
INDUS	-0.125982	-18.27313	0.0000
Constant	0.086394	1.967297	0.0574
R ²		0.21	
F statistics		3.21	
Prob (F-statics)		0.02	

OLS regression analysis

Another regression should be conducted to test the impact of board characteristics on earnings management for Saudi family businesses from 2019-2020. Table 5 presents the ordinary least squares (OLS) estimates for the model that analyses the impact of independent outside directors on earnings management in family businesses from 2019 to 2020. Surprisingly, the results show no significant effect of (BIND, BSIZ, FSIZ, LEV, ROA, or COVID-19) on (ADACC) except that industry has a negative and significant impact on discretionary accruals (ADACC), implying that industrial firms have a lower likelihood of manipulating earnings in Saudi family businesses. Overall, this regression is weak, owing to a p-value of all variables > 0.05 except the industry variable, which significantly impacts EM. However, R² is 0.29, implying that approximately 29% of the dependent variable (ADACC) variance is caused by independent variables (BIND, BSIZ).

Table 5: OLS regression analysis for the Saudi family businesses from 2019-2020 after adding dummy variables

Variable	coefficient	t-Statistic	prob.
<i>Independent variables</i>			
BIND	-0.168287	-0.688154	0.4960
BSIZ	-0.038299	-2.014378	0.0519
<i>Control Variables</i>			
FSIZ	0.019446	1.046443	0.3027
LEV	0.001010	0.010256	0.9919
ROA	0.271677	1.577373	0.2339
<i>Dummy variables</i>			
COVID-19	0.046946	1.211966	0.2339
INDUS	-0.101902	-2.084899	0.0447
Constant	0.062585	0.162492	0.8719
R ²		0.29	
F-statistics		2.02	
Prob (F-statics)		0.08	

Subsample analysis

The primary purpose of this study is to examine the impact of independent outside directors and board size on the EM phenomenon in Saudi family businesses pre-COVID-19 and post-COVID-19. This goal can be accomplished by conducting separate regressions in 2019 and 2020 to provide accurate results. Tables 6 and 7 indicate that independent outside directors and board size (BIND,

BSIZ) do not significantly impact discretionary accruals (ADACC) pre-COVID-19 and post-COVID-19. This implies that the large board size and the presence of independent outside directors do not mitigate the manipulation of earnings in Saudi family businesses from 2019 to 2020. So, the results fail to support the hypotheses of this study. Validating this result requires a robustness check.

Table 6: Testing the impact of independent outside directors and board size on earnings management in Saudi family businesses pre-COVID-19.

Variable	Coefficient	t-Statistic	prob.
BIND	-0.061170	-0.194454	0.8480
BSIZ	-0.015835	-0.715095	0.4837
Constant	0.248434	0.936544	0.3614

Table 7: Testing the impact of independent outside directors and board size on earnings management in Saudi family businesses post-COVID-19.

Variable	Coefficient	t-Statistic	prob.
BIND	-0.245932	-0.609292	0.5499
BSIZ	-0.039958	-1.464696	0.1603
Constant	0.559296	1.635664	0.1193

Discussion

The research discusses the impact of independent outside directors and board size on the earnings management phenomenon in Saudi family businesses pre-COVID-19 and post-COVID-19. After splitting the sample based on the years and solving the heteroscedasticity issue, the findings of this research indicated that there is no robust relationship between the presence of independent outside directors and EM practices in Saudi family businesses, pre-COVID-19; hence, hypothesis *H1* is rejected. On the one hand, the results are in line with the previous studies (Abdul & Haneem, 2006; Jaggi et al., 2009; Saidat et al., 2018; Bansa, 2021), as they found the ineffectiveness of the board's independence in limiting EM practices in family businesses in Malaysia, India, Jordan and, Hong Kong owing to the ownership concentration. Besides, they are not full-time employees unfamiliar with the company's operations. Independent outside directors are less effective in family businesses since they are appointed based on family or friendship ties.

On the other hand, this finding contradicts previous studies (Chi et al., 2015; Vieira, 2016) in Taiwan and Portugal, where they found that independent outside directors prevent EM practices in family businesses.

However, the study's sample follows the requirements of the CG code with the minimum number of independent outside directors. This may be attributed to the sample size, which is small because this research was limited to non-financial family businesses listed on the Tadawul in 2019 and 2020, which affected the results of this study.

Independence may not affect the EM in family businesses, but members' values and ethics influence their behavior as they value the company's reputation. Therefore, the sample size or the study's method may explain the differences between these findings.

Concerning the board size, this study's results indicated an inverse relationship between board size and EM pre-COVID-19 in Saudi family businesses, which supports hypothesis *H3*. To elaborate further, the result before solving the heteroscedasticity issue was insignificant, but it has changed to be significant after solving this issue. Large board size has a considerable role in mitigating EM in Saudi family businesses pre-COVID-19, and the average board size of this study was approximately eight members. The results of this study are consistent with previous studies that examined the effectiveness of large board sizes in reducing manipulated earnings in the US, Bahrain, and Egypt (Marrakchi Chtourou, 2001; Alareeni, 2018; Abdou et al., 2021). Hence, it is important to increase board size to reduce EM practices. Large boards are more effective because of their diversity of skills, expertise, and gender and how they manage their firms' resources. This aligns with resource dependence and upper-echelon theories (Abdou et al., 2021).

In contrast, a positive correlation exists between board size and earnings management in Malaysia, Europe, and Ghana (Hashim & Devi, 2008; García-Ramos & García-Olalla, 2011; Agyeman, 2020). This supports the existence of small boards as the members effectively manage the interrelationships between board members and take less time to make decisions than large boards. Finally, there is no significant effect between independent outside directors and board size on EM post-COVID-19; thus, the results do not support hypotheses *H2* and *H4*. A possible explanation is the spread of COVID-19, which influences the relationship between independent and dependent variables. This is consistent with the previous studies as they did not find a significant effect between board size and firm performance during COVID-19 (Khatib et al., 2021; Ricapito, 2024). Capital Market Authority has taken several procedures to address the risks of COVID-19, including extending the statutory period of public disclosure periods of the initial financial statements of listed companies for the periods ending 29/02/2020 and 31/03/2020 (CMA, 2022). In addition to working remotely and owing to the difficulty of dealing with technology, it is hard for the BOD to restrict unethical behaviour during the COVID-19 quarantine. During such times, boards must apply new technologies to reduce financial and administrative corruption.

Implications of the results

Pre-COVID-19, the large board had a vital role in reducing EM in Saudi family businesses under normal conditions due to different expertise, age, education, and knowledge, and this aligns with upper echelon theory (Hambrick & Mason, 1984). Regarding agency theory, larger boards will improve governance, which helps to effectively oversee and control management and reduce manipulation in financial statements and agency costs. The pandemic has affected the world, and there is no significant relationship between board size and independent outside directors on EM in Saudi family businesses post-COVID-19. The independent directors shifted their focus from essential roles in management oversight and promoting accountability to maintaining liquidity and corporate continuity. In short, external conditions such as unexpected crises will affect the fundamental roles of the BOD.

Conclusion, Limitations, and Recommendations

COVID-19 continues to have a profound impact on the economy and businesses. This study examines the effect of board characteristics on EM in Saudi family firms pre- and post-COVID-19. Financial reporting should reflect the economic reality of the companies and should not be manipulated since investors base their decisions on it. Loss of credibility in financial statements damages the company's reputation. Family businesses have highly concentrated ownership, which helps to lower the unemployment rates and attract foreign direct investment. This study is a sample of 21 Saudi family firms listed on the Saudi Stock Exchange (Tadawul) from 2019-2020 (yielding 42 firm-year observations) in nine sectors, excluding all non-financial and non-family businesses. The results indicate that board size is the only internal CG mechanism that negatively and significantly impacts EM practices in Saudi family businesses pre-COVID-19. On the other hand, the results report that independent outside directors and board size have no significant effect on EM post-COVID-19. No doubt, COVID-19 causes many difficulties due to work-from-home mandates. During this time, the CMA extended the statutory period for the public disclosure of the initial financial reports of listed companies (CMA,2022). Hence, the COVID-19 quarantine challenges the BOD in terms of limiting unethical behaviours, so this crisis has affected all board characteristics.

The limitations of this study are: firstly, some family businesses were excluded owing to the unavailability of their data, and after splitting the sample based on the years, the sample size became small, and this may affect the accuracy of the results; hence, it is difficult to generalize the results. Secondly, this study focused only on two characteristics of the BOD, independent outside directors and board size, and its data were manually collected owing to the unavailability of this data in the Bloomberg databases.

The study recommends that mental independence is essential to improve the effectiveness of independent outside directors since apparent independence alone is insufficient and may harm the companies. It should also be ensured that there are no family relationships between independent outside directors and other board members to mitigate the manipulation of earnings in Saudi family businesses. Also, it recommends that the Capital Market Authority provide guidelines and courses on the negative effects of EM practices on the accounting and auditing profession, companies, shareholders, and the state's economy, as well as enact strict penalties for its practitioners. Moreover, it recommends providing a list of Saudi family companies on Tadawul's website to assist the researchers in collecting and analysing their data. Determining if a company listed in the primary market is a family company takes a long time and affects the reliability of the study's findings. Future research could compare the effects of CG mechanisms on EM between developing and developed countries pre- and post-COVID-19 to evaluate how effective the CG mechanisms are at mitigating EM. Other CG mechanisms also have the potential to be studied, such as gender diversity on BOD in Saudi Arabia, since Saudi Vision 2030 supports and encourages the presence of females on boards to increase female participation in the labour force.

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